

Management of Two Extensive Radicular Cysts in The Anterior Maxillary Region: A Combined Endodontic and Surgical Approach

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ABSTRACT

Traumatic injury to the front teeth is common and can lead to cysts over time.

These lesions are usually asymptomatic but can lead to slow-growing tumefaction in the affected region, causing discomfort and affecting adjacent structures. Treatment is still under discussion and the first step is usually non-surgical endodontic therapy. However, for large lesions, endodontic treatment alone is not sufficient and should be combined with surgery.

This paper presents a rare case report of two large radicular cysts in the anterior maxillary region that required a combined endodontic and surgical approach for effective management.

Keywords: Apicoectomy; Endodontic surgery; Cyst; MTA; Outcomes; Periapical healing

INTRODUCTION

Traumatic injuries to the anterior teeth are common and can have significant consequences over time. One potential complication that can result from such injuries is the formation of a cyst, which develops as a result of the stimulation and proliferation of the epithelial remnants of Malassez in the periodontal ligament following dental trauma. In the early stages, this development is often asymptomatic, making it difficult to detect without a proper examination.^[1,2] However, the cyst can gradually grow and lead to the development of a slow-growing tumefaction in the affected area, causing discomfort and affecting adjacent structures.

The management of these lesions is still a topic of debate, and the first step typically involves non-surgical endodontic treatment. However, in large lesions, endodontic treatment alone is not sufficient, and it should be associated with surgery.^[3]

This paper presents a case report of two large radicular cysts in the maxillary anterior region that required a combined endodontic and surgical approach for effective management. The lesions had completely resorbed the maxillary nasal floor, which adds complexity to the treatment process.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 22-year-old male patient was referred to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics of the Military Principal Hospital of Instruction in Tunis with the chief complaint of pain, swelling and pus discharge in the left anterior maxillary region for the past 2 months. Dental history revealed a traumatic fall 8 months ago involving the upper front teeth, but no dental treatment was sought at that time. Clinical examination revealed facial asymmetry with a swelling of approximately 4 cm in diameter. Intraoral examination revealed the deformation of the vestibular bone, the presence of a well-defined fluctuating swelling extending from tooth 12 to tooth 22. Teeth 21 and 22 showed discoloration and chipping at the incisal edge of the crown of tooth 21, while tooth 11 showed a root tip state. Vitality testing showed no response in these teeth. Affected teeth 21 and 22 were slightly tender to percussion and showed grade 1 mobility. The intraoral periapical radiograph showed a unilocular radiolucency extending between the roots of the affected teeth (Figure 1, A). In contrast, the Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) scan revealed two large, well-defined, expansive radiolucent lesions around the apices of teeth 11, 21 and 22. The axial view revealed severe bony expansion with thinning and perforation of both the labial and palatal cortical plates (Figure 1, B).

In the coronal view, there was evident disruption in the structure of the nasal floor. (Figure 1,C). The radiographic findings suggest the diagnosis of two radicular cysts associated with teeth 11, 21 and 22.

Figure 1: Preoperative radiological investigations: Periapical radiograph (A) and CBCT scans (B and C) showed the presence of two periapical radiolucent lesions around the apices of teeth 11, 21 and 22, along with the expansion of the bony defect into the nasal floor.

Due to the significant size of the radicular cysts and the extensive bone loss, the treatment plan was determined to be root canal therapy for teeth 21 and 22, followed by surgery to remove the cysts. This surgical procedure included enucleation of the cysts, apicectomy and retrograde filling of both teeth 21 and 22. After obtaining informed consent from the patient, endodontic root canal treatment was performed. A calcium hydroxide dressing was applied for 15 days. Endodontic obturation was performed with gutta-percha and a bioceramic sealer BioRoot™ RCS (Septodont) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Root canal obturation of teeth 21 and 22.

The endodontic treatment was followed by the surgical phase. A full-thickness mucoperiosteal flap was raised from the maxillary left canine (tooth 23) to the maxillary left lateral incisor (tooth 22). Flap reflection showed the cystic lesion at the apical end of the affected teeth, together with dehiscence along the length of the root tip. Cystic enucleation was performed and tooth 11 was extracted (Figure 3). Extensive expansion of the cyst within the maxilla reaching supero-posteriorly to the nasal base was observe (Figure 4). During surgical enucleation, the nasal mucosa adhered to the cystic lining. A careful surgical technique was used to remove the cyst completely.

Figure 3: Cyst's enucleation and tooth 11 extraction.

Figure 4: Nasal floor bone defect.

After complete removal of the cysts, an apicoectomy was performed using the Zekrya drill (Figure 5). A 3 mm segment was precisely resected from the apical root tips of the teeth using a 90-degree angle. The bur was perpendicular to the long axis of each root. Saline irrigation was then used to carefully debride the cavity, effectively removing necrotic debris, gutta-percha fragments and any residual material. The root-end cavities were prepared to a depth of 3 mm using an ultrasonic device with an angled ultrasonic tip. The cavities were then filled with MTA Biorep (Itena) (Figure 6,7).

Figure 5: Apicoectomy of the root ends of teeth 21 and 22.

Figure 6: Obturation of the prepared cavities with MTA Biorep (Itena)

Figure 7: (A,B) Post-operative radiographs controlling the retrograde filling.

The excised specimen was sent for histopathological examination. Post-operative medication and instructions were given to the patient. Ten days later, the sutures were removed, and follow-up examinations showed no swelling or pain. The postoperative OPG at 8 months showed continuous bone formation. The lesion revealed signs of healing. The radiolucency was decreased, with increased bone regeneration activity and more trabeculae filling the lesion (Figure 8).

Figure 8: OPG control radiograph after 8 months showed an increase in bone density.

DISCUSSION

The prevalence of apical cysts varies widely, from 6% to 44%. These lesions are thought to result from the stimulation and proliferation of epithelial remnants of Malassez in the periodontal ligament, triggered by factors such as caries, dental trauma or failed dental treatment. As noted by Shear et al, most apical cysts are asymptomatic and painless, develop gradually, and are often discovered incidentally during routine radiographic examinations as large periapical radiolucencies involving the apex of one or more teeth over time.^[4] These cysts may regress, remain stable or increase in size. The optimal management of apical cysts remains a topic of debate and is guided by several factors, including the origin and extent of the lesion, its relationship to vital structures, clinical presentation, systemic health considerations and patient cooperation.^[5] Initial treatment usually involves non-surgical endodontic treatment. However, for large lesions, endodontic treatment alone may not be sufficient and additional surgical intervention may be required.^[6,7] Our clinical case presents an unusual occurrence of an extensive defect extending from the upper right central incisor to the upper left lateral incisor, resulting in destruction of the nasal floor. Such cases are typically chronic and progress slowly, leading to tooth mobility. Large bony lesions that completely penetrate the bone require a combined approach of endodontic treatment and periapical surgery.^[5] Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) played a crucial role in accurately assessing the volume and extent of the cysts.^[8] It also helped to identify two distinct lesions that were not visible on 2D radiography. Studies have shown that CBCT provides earlier and more reliable detection of apical periodontitis than periapical radiographs.^[1,9,10] In this case, root canal treatment was carried out over multiple appointments with temporary calcium hydroxide dressings. In cases of chronic periapical lesions, it is crucial to use intracanal dressing with calcium hydroxide to achieve a significant reduction in microbial load. Calcium hydroxide dressing can penetrate deeper into areas that are unreachable by instruments or irrigation solutions, such as dentinal tubules and ramifications. Due to its hygroscopic properties, calcium hydroxide has demonstrated high clinical effectiveness in exudate reduction.^[11,12] Research indicates a minimum two-week placement for calcium hydroxide medicament to achieve optimal antimicrobial activity.^[13] BioRoot™ RCS, a bioceramics-based sealer, was used for root canal obturation due to its superior antimicrobial activity against endodontic pathogens compared to other sealers. Additionally, it has the ability to promote healing.^[14,15,16]

The main objective of root-end surgery is to resect the root end containing the complex infected anatomy, followed by preparation of the root-end cavity, debridement and effective sealing of the exposed termini with an appropriate filling material.^[17] Root-end preparations were conducted using ultrasonic tips, reaching a depth of 3 mm and following the longitudinal axis of each root, centered within the respective root canals. In the past, periapical surgery involved the use of surgical burs for root-end preparation. However, conventional rotary burs are susceptible to errors, such as misalignment with the root axis, incomplete removal of isthmus, and the necessity for larger osteotomies. In contrast, ultrasonic tips enable more conservative osteotomies and deliver cleaner and deeper apical root-end preparations.^[18,19] A recent meta-analysis highlighted that the use of ultrasonics in root-end cavity preparation significantly outperformed traditional bur-based techniques, leading to higher clinical success rates.^[20] A suitable root-end filling material should have a combination of desirable properties to ensure a successful clinical outcome. Biocompatibility is paramount, as the material will be in direct contact with living tissues.^[21] Exceptional sealing properties are also essential to prevent bacterial leakage and promote healing.

In addition, bacteriostatic or bactericidal properties would be beneficial to combat residual microorganisms. Finally, radiopacity is essential for clear visualisation on radiographs, allowing accurate assessment of filling placement and post-operative follow-up.^[18,22] MTA is often the material of choice for root-end filling due to its superior biocompatibility, bacteriostatic activity and favorable sealing properties.^[14] Considering the rarity of this presentation and the extent of the lesions, a combined surgical approach with endodontic treatment was deemed necessary to achieve rapid and effective rehabilitation. Post-operative care and regular monitoring of the healing process are essential to assess treatment success and minimize the risk of infection. Considering the potential risks, benefits and drawbacks of each therapeutic option was essential in determining the most appropriate treatment plan for this particular clinical case.^[23]

CONCLUSION

In the present case, apical surgery was combined with endodontic treatment due to the presence of swelling and the size and extent of the apical lesions.

The advantage of enucleation is the prompt rehabilitation, leading to fewer follow-up appointments, making it a suitable option for patients with poor compliance. However, enucleation has drawbacks, including creating a large defect and potentially damaging nearby structures during the surgical procedure.

The heading "Declarations":

- 1/ Ethics approval and consent to participate: 'Not applicable' for that section.
- 2/ Consent for publication: The patient has provided written informed consent for the publication of the case report.
- 3/ Availability of data and materials: The data (figures) supporting our article are available upon request. Researchers interested in accessing the dataset can contact the corresponding author, Mayada Jemâa, via email at "dr.jemaamayada@gmail.com". The author will promptly respond to inquiries and provide the necessary information for accessing the data.
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- 6/ Authors' contributions: Fadia Ajili and Mayada Jemâa wrote the main manuscript text. Olfa Zaghden and Hichem Mehrez prepared the figures. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

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